

Deliverable D1.8

Wider Communication Strategy - final evaluation and review

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1. Executive Summary

Engagement with citizens, patients and healthcare professionals is essential to the long-term success of the 1+MG initiative. Trust, understanding and informed participation need to be built early and sustained over time, including during phases when technical infrastructure and governance arrangements are still under development. Early communication supports transparency, manages expectations and creates the conditions for future uptake.

This deliverable presents the final review and evaluation of the GDI Wider Communications Strategy, as defined in Task 1.4 of the Description of Action and detailed in D1.3. It focuses on engagement with citizens and healthcare professionals and on national capacity building to support implementation by 1+MG Member States. This work is distinct from project-level communications (covered by D1.2), which focus on promoting GDI project activities.

The work reviewed comprises three areas: (i) creation, dissemination and tracking of 1+MG outreach videos; (ii) development, dissemination and tracking of guidelines and templates for national communication strategies; and (iii) capacity-building activities to inform healthcare professional engagement and training recommendations. Activities were led by the ELIXIR Hub, with national dissemination and tracking coordinated through ISCIII, Spain and healthcare professional engagement led by INSA, Portugal.

The evaluation applied a process, output and outcome indicator approach, combining quantitative monitoring data (website, social media, newsletter/email metrics and Zenodo downloads) with qualitative evidence from stakeholder consultations and Member State reporting via the 1+MG National Mirror Groups. LinkedIn and YouTube metrics have been tracked throughout the project and used to support iterative improvement.

The evaluation shows measurable reach and engagement for citizen-facing communications at European level. The 1+MG video series reached 5,345 views across YouTube and LinkedIn, and the “For citizens” section of the GDI website functioned as a stable reference point for accessible information. At national level, D1.3 guidance demonstrated strong uptake (516 views and 382 downloads), indicating active retrieval for reuse.

Tracking between January 2025 and January 2026 shows early but measurable progress in the development of national communication strategies, with fewer Member States reporting no strategy in place. However, most remain at an early or intermediate stage. National uptake of outreach videos is similarly limited at this point, reflecting the time and capacity required to move from shared European resources to active national dissemination.

Overall, the findings confirm that GDI communications and capacity-building activities made a practical contribution to the 1+MG initiative and provide a strong foundation for continued and

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expanded engagement through the Genome EDIC structure, where these activities can be sustained and scaled.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels</p>	No

<p>(national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Methods

The evaluation was conducted as a final review in January 2026, covering performance from the start of each activity until that point. In parallel, monitoring of GDI LinkedIn and YouTube was carried out on an ongoing basis during implementation to support iterative improvement of project communications.

The evaluation included the development and dissemination of 1+MG videos (EU and national level), national strategy guidelines and factsheets, engagement with patient educators via EUPATI, and capacity-building activities to inform healthcare professional training recommendations, including a focus group and follow-on survey development.

Evidence for the evaluation was drawn from: website analytics (Matomo), platform analytics for LinkedIn and YouTube, newsletter/email metrics (Mailchimp), event monitoring records where applicable (registrations and attendance), download statistics (Zenodo), partner reporting from Member States via the 1+MG National Mirror Groups, and stakeholder consultations.

The evaluation relied on the availability and comparability of monitoring data across channels and Member States. Levels of national reporting and implementation detail varied, which may limit direct comparison between countries. Engagement metrics indicate reach and interaction but do not, on their own, demonstrate changes in awareness, attitudes, or behaviour. In addition, some longer-term outcomes of national capacity building may emerge beyond the project reporting period.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Review of activities

Table 1 lists the activities completed as part of the GDI Wider Communications Strategy. They can be split into 3 main categories:

1. Creation, dissemination and tracking of 1+MG promotional videos
2. Creation, dissemination and tracking of guidelines for national communications strategy creation
3. Recommendations for healthcare professionals training and engagement

The final column of the table indicated the organisation responsible for the activities. The external Relations team at the ELIXIR Hub, based in Hinxton, UK have led the activities and been responsible for creation of the main outputs. The S.G. de Programas Internacionales de Investigación y Relaciones Institucionales team at the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII) in Madrid, Spain have carried out national level dissemination. And the Department of Health Promotion and NCD

Prevention team at the Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), in Lisbon, Portugal are working on the recommendations for healthcare professionals training and engagement.

All activities in the Description of Action for task 1.4 (Wider Communications Strategy) are either complete or underway. This final review is scheduled for 8 months prior to the end of the GDI project so there is time to incorporate findings into the remaining implementation of the strategy. It also allows time to complete the three outstanding activities. These are:

1. Tracking of video promotion and communication strategy implementation at the national level
2. Engagement with patient educators via EUPATI
3. Recommendations for healthcare professionals training and engagement

The tracking of uptake at the national level runs for the duration of the project. Engagement with patient educators via EUPATI did not start until relatively late in the project, as it followed unsuccessful attempts to engage with a range of European patient organisations. The production of recommendations for healthcare professionals training and engagement is still underway, the aim is to finish this task before the end of the project to allow time for dissemination of results by the ELIXIR Hub.

Date of completion	Activity title	Activity details	Who
3/2025	Creation of 1+MG videos for citizens and healthcare professionals ¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consultations with GDI project experts and EC representatives to understand purpose and content of videos ● Creation of video proposal and tender ● Selection of video provider ● Selection of interviewees and scripting of video - with input and approval of GDI Management Board ● Shooting interviews and creating motion graphics ● Postproduction editing including review by GDI Management Board and EC ● Amendments and final approval 	ELIXIR
3/2025	Dissemination of videos at European level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GDI news release and social media ● Promotion of videos in GDI and B1MGplus newsletter ● Creation of new section "For citizens" on GDI website, including transcripts of videos ● Creation of longer interview videos ● Paid-for promotion of videos on LinkedIn 	ELIXIR

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UyQ2Uo8bXgY&list=PLweO8RYcVPDMFzSXDUoyEgOvvMS-BllaT>

3/2025	Dissemination of videos at national level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Email circulation to 1+MG National Mirror Group points of contact Circulation of simple video translation instructions Indication that tracking video promotion and translation would follow 	ISCIII
11/2025	Video promotion and translation guidelines ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detailed video promotion and translation guidelines produced Included in video tracking request to 1+MG National Mirror Groups 	ELIXIR
Ongoing	Tracking promotion and translation of videos at national level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First tracking January 2026 via 1+MG National Mirror Groups Tracking planned in September 2026 	ISCIII
11/2024	National strategy guidelines and factsheets ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultation with EC on content and branding Drafted content for review by GDI Management Board and GDI Stakeholder Forum Incorporated feedback for approval by the Management Board 	ELIXIR
1/2025	Dissemination of national strategy guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Email circulation to 1+MG National Mirror Group points of contact Promotion in GDI newsletter 	ISCIII
Ongoing	Tracking implementation of national strategy guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tracking carried out in January 2025 and January 2026 via 1+MG National Mirror Groups Tracking planned in September 2026 	ISCIII
Ongoing	Engagement with patient educators via EUPATI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Held 3 meetings since August 2025 with EUPATI, with EUPATI Director General and EU Project Officer. EUPATI patient experts to provide feedback on 1+MG patient factsheets. GDI and EUPATI to make links at the national level 	ELIXIR
Ongoing	Recommendations for healthcare professionals training and engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Held a focus group with 11 healthcare professionals to understand needs for training and engagement Focus group outcomes used to develop a survey targeting healthcare professionals Survey results will be used to develop recommendations for training and engagement of healthcare professionals 	INSA

² https://drive.google.com/file/d/12U2LPUYGgjuEx_XytVvxiiIR8G-X6-IG/view

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/14014009>

Table 1: Activities completed as part of the GDI Wider Communications Strategy

4.2 Evaluation

The evaluation was structured around the commitments set out in the Description of Action, which emphasised developing guidance, resources and actions to engage key stakeholder groups, and supporting implementation at national level through the 1+MG National Mirror Groups. The evaluation therefore focused on:

1. **Citizen-facing communications:** development of reusable content suitable for national dissemination, including short video content.
2. **Patient engagement:** engagement with European-level patient communities and patient educator networks to support awareness and trust.
3. **Healthcare professional engagement:** consultation and structured input to inform recommendations for training and awareness, recognising the importance of healthcare professional involvement for long-term sustainability of the 1+MG initiative.
4. **National capacity building:** provision of guidance and templates to support Member States in developing strategies aligned with national context, including D1.3⁴ guidance materials.

A combined process, output and outcome indicator framework was used:

- **Process indicators** assessed how activities were implemented (e.g. coordination with governance structures and national points of contact, and establishment of tracking mechanisms).
- **Output indicators** assessed what was produced and disseminated (e.g. guidance materials and outreach assets).
- **Outcome indicators** assessed evidence of reach, engagement and uptake (e.g. interaction with published outputs and evidence of reuse at national level).

This approach reflects the intent of D1.3, which recognises that national communications approaches will vary and that countries will need to define target groups, select channels, plan engagement actions, and implement monitoring.

5. Results

5.1 Citizen-facing communications (videos and web content)

Website reach and visibility

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/14014009>

Citizen-facing content was consolidated through a dedicated “For citizens” page on the GDI website⁵. By January 2026, this page received 353 total page views. The accompanying news item announcing the 1+MG initiative video release⁶ received 146 total page views.

These results show measurable traffic to citizen-oriented content during the evaluation period and indicate that the website was used as a stable access point for video material and supporting information.

Video performance (YouTube and LinkedIn)

Across all videos, the total performance recorded by January 2026 was:

- Total views: 5,345
- YouTube views: 1,457
- YouTube impressions: 6,610
- LinkedIn views: 3,888
- LinkedIn impressions: 10,727

The strongest-performing single video by views was “Genomic Data Is Transforming Patient Care: The 1+MG Initiative Explained” with 790 YouTube views. The four short interview videos embedded and promoted via LinkedIn reached between 492 and 1,784 total views each, demonstrating consistent engagement across the series.

Three longer-form YouTube videos were promoted via LinkedIn using outbound links rather than embedded posts, resulting in YouTube views without corresponding LinkedIn video view counts. This distinction was taken into account in interpreting comparative performance across formats.

Social media engagement (organic posts)

Organic LinkedIn posts promoting the videos and citizen-facing materials generated consistent visibility and engagement. Across individual posts, impressions ranged from 675 to 3,276, with click-through rates between 0.023 and 0.063, and engagement rates between 0.05 and 0.102. Posts linking to the “For citizens” page and video content resulted in repeatable click activity, indicating active user behaviour beyond passive viewing.

Paid promotion (LinkedIn campaigns)

Paid dissemination was used to extend visibility and reach beyond organic audiences:

- Healthcare professionals video ad campaign: 48,055 views, 95,586 impressions, 122 clicks
- Citizen/patient ad campaign: 6,709 views, 11,243 impressions, 9 clicks

⁵ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/for-citizens>

⁶ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/1+mg-initiative-video>

Overall, the healthcare professional campaign reached a substantially higher scale than the citizen/patient campaign. This difference is consistent with the larger target professional audience base on LinkedIn compared with citizen and patient segments.

5.2 Patient engagement and patient educator community

The DoA envisaged engagement with European umbrella patient organisations; however, this route did not progress as expected in practice. Engagement activities were therefore adapted to focus on collaboration with EUPATI⁷, which offered a practical route into patient educator networks.

During the evaluation period, three meetings were held with EUPATI (from August 2025 onwards), with the EUPATI Director General and GDI EC Project Officer. Next steps include 1+MG partners and EUPATI networks developing national-level linkages and the EUPATI patient experts providing feedback on the patient factsheets in D1.3. The patient factsheets will be updated and reissued as a result.

5.3 Healthcare professional engagement and recommendations

Capacity building targeting healthcare professionals progressed through structured consultation activity led by INSA.

- A focus group with 11 healthcare professionals was held to identify needs and expectations regarding training, engagement, and communication relating to 1+MG.
- Findings were used to design a follow-up survey targeting healthcare professionals, intended to inform recommendations for awareness-raising and training.
- At the time of evaluation (January 2026), this strand was still in progress, with recommendations not yet finalised.

This reflects partial completion at the evaluation cut-off point, with further results expected once the survey and recommendations are completed.

5.4 National capacity building (guidance and national-level uptake)

Uptake of D1.3 guidance materials

The primary national capacity-building resource, D1.3 guidance and templates for national communications and outreach strategies, demonstrated strong access and reuse signals via Zenodo:

- 516 views
- 382 downloads

⁷ <https://eupati.eu>

This indicates that the resource was not only accessed but also actively retrieved for potential reuse and adaptation, consistent with its intent to support national planning and implementation.

National dissemination and tracking via Member State structures

Dissemination and tracking were supported through collaboration with 1+MG National Mirror Groups via ISCIII. The guidelines were circulated in January 2025 and Member States were asked *Is there a 1+MG communication strategy for citizens/healthcare professionals in [country]?*. The videos were circulated in March 2025 along with translation guidelines. A second round of tracking was performed in January 2026, which included tracking the status of the videos, and more detailed guidance on video promotion was circulated. A final round of tracking is planned before the end of the project.

The results are shown in Figure 1.

January 2025

January 2026

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Is there a 1+MG communication strategy for citizens/healthcare professionals in [country]?

- No
- Available locally as a bottom-up initiative with specific target audiences
- A national strategy for communication is under development
- A national strategy for communication is widely implemented, with dedicated funds
- A national strategy for communication is widely implemented, with dedicated funds and regular monitoring, and includes tools for active involvement of the public in general, minorities and youth in particular

Figure 1: Results of communication strategy tracking in January 2025 and January 2026

In both January 2025 and 2026, there was a 68% response rate, although 3 new countries reported for the first time in 2026 and 3 countries responded in 2025 only. Baseline tracking showed that dedicated 1+MG communication strategies remained at an early stage of maturity across Member States. For communication targeted at citizens, 62% of respondents reported that no strategy is in place, while 25% indicated that a national strategy is under development and 13% reported locally available, bottom-up initiatives. For communication targeted at healthcare professionals, responses suggest a more developed landscape, with 44% reporting local bottom-up initiatives and 19% indicating that a national strategy is under development, while 37% still reported that no strategy is in place. No Member State reported a strategy that is widely implemented with dedicated funds and monitoring.

Tracking in January 2026 showed an improvement in the maturity of communication strategies for both citizens and healthcare professionals, although most Member States remain at an early or intermediate stage. For citizen-focused communication, the proportion of respondents reporting that no strategy is in place decreased from 62% to 44%. Meanwhile, the percentage of strategies under development increased from 25% to 31%, and the proportion of locally available, bottom-up initiatives increased from 13% to 19%. One Member State, the Czech Republic, reported that a national strategy is widely implemented with dedicated funds. No Member State reported a strategy that is widely implemented with dedicated funds and regular monitoring.

A similar pattern was observed for communication targeting healthcare professionals. The proportion reporting no strategy in place decreased from 37% to 31%, while locally available, bottom-up initiatives remained the most frequently reported approach (38%, compared with 44% at baseline). The proportion reporting a national strategy under development increased from 19% to 25%, and the Czech Republic reported a widely implemented national strategy with dedicated funds. As for citizen communication, no Member State reported a strategy that is widely implemented with dedicated funds and regular monitoring.

In January 2026, Member States were asked *What is the status of three GDI outreach videos, circulated in March 2025?*. The response rate was the same as for the communications strategy question (68%), and the results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Results of video tracking in January 2025 and January 2026

The first round of national tracking suggests that uptake of the 1+MG outreach videos has been limited. The majority of respondents (63%) reported that the videos are not in use nationally. Around a third (31%) reported that the videos are available in English for national communication to citizens and healthcare professionals, but without evidence of wider rollout. One Member State, the Czech Republic reported translation of the subtitles and use in a communications campaign. As of writing (February 2026) the video subtitles have also been translated into French.

In both the tracking of the communication strategies and the video uptake, many Member States used free text to indicate their planned efforts in these areas, and their parallel work on outreach to citizens around genomic medicine.

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6. Discussion

6.1 The importance of citizen and healthcare professional engagement

The 1+MG initiative depends on sustained participation and confidence from multiple stakeholder groups, including citizens, patients and healthcare professionals. Citizen-facing outreach supports transparency and trust, patient engagement ensures that concerns and expectations are reflected in governance and implementation, and healthcare professional engagement is particularly important for translating infrastructure and research benefits into clinical practice.

The GDI communication activities contributed to this objective by producing accessible videos and factsheets and by supporting Member States with guidance and tools to develop national communication and engagement approaches. This aligns with the intent of D1.3, which emphasises that national engagement approaches need to be tailored to country context and implemented through national structures.

6.2 Interpretation of results

The evaluation results show measurable reach and engagement across multiple channels. The 1+MG video series achieved a combined total of 5,345 views, with LinkedIn accounting for the majority of recorded views and impressions. This indicates that professional and institutional networks were a strong dissemination route for video content and that short interview-style materials can generate consistent engagement when promoted through established channels.

The “For citizens” website page and related news article also recorded clear audience traffic, indicating that the website functioned as a stable reference point where citizens and stakeholders could access curated information and video content in one place. While page view numbers were modest compared with social media impressions, this is consistent with the different roles of owned channels (web pages used as reference points) versus social channels (used to generate visibility and drive traffic).

Tracking at Member State level provides additional context for interpreting these results. Comparison of January 2025 and January 2026 tracking indicates a gradual shift away from the absence of formal communication strategies towards early-stage development and locally implemented initiatives for both citizens and healthcare professionals. While most Member States remain at an early or intermediate stage, the reduction in reports of “no strategy in place” suggests growing awareness of the need for structured communication and engagement approaches.

6.3 National capacity building

The national capacity-building component, centred on D1.3 guidance and templates for national communications and outreach strategies, showed strong evidence of uptake through Zenodo usage

(516 views and 382 downloads). This suggests the deliverable was not only accessed but actively retrieved for reuse and adaptation.

National implementation depends on sufficient capacity and resourcing, a key message from D1.3. Communication and engagement activity requires dedicated time, skills and often budget for translation, national stakeholder coordination, campaign delivery, and sustained feedback loops. Strategy guidance and tools can support and accelerate national planning, but they do not replace the need for funded national delivery mechanisms.

National tracking of the 1+MG outreach videos further illustrates the current stage of maturity. The first round of video tracking (January 2026) showed that most Member States had not yet actively adopted the videos for national use, with 63% reporting that the videos were not in use and around one third reporting availability in English only. Only one Member State reported translation of subtitles and use within a communications campaign. This pattern is consistent with the early-stage maturity observed for national strategies and highlights the time and capacity required to move from availability of central resources to active national dissemination.

6.4 Continuation through the EDIC

Engagement with citizens and healthcare professionals should be maintained and strengthened through the Genome EDIC structure, building on the early progress observed in national strategy development and initial uptake of shared communication resources. Long-term impact requires national amplification, sustained stakeholder relationships and dedicated resourcing. These activities could include (i) continued development of high-quality reusable citizen-facing content; (ii) deeper and more structured patient educator engagement through EUPATI and national counterparts; (iii) implementation of healthcare professional recommendations; and (iv) ongoing national tracking and support through the National Mirror Groups.

6.5 Revision of the D1.3 guidelines

A revised version of the D1.3 guidelines is planned by the end of the project. This updated version will incorporate learning and feedback from implementation and stakeholder engagement, including patient input and the guidance for video promotion and dissemination. EUPATI contact information will also be added, along with a link to the healthcare professional training guidance, if available. This update will strengthen the practical usability of the guidance and support more consistent national implementation beyond the project period.

7. Conclusions & impact

This deliverable provides the final review and evaluation of GDI communication and capacity-building activities supporting the 1+MG initiative, focusing on engagement with citizens, patients and healthcare professionals, and support for national implementation by 1+MG Member States.

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The evaluation shows that citizen-facing communications achieved measurable reach and engagement across multiple channels. The 1+MG video series reached a combined total of 5,345 views across YouTube and LinkedIn, with LinkedIn accounting for the majority of recorded views and impressions. The dedicated "For citizens" section of the GDI website and supporting news content also received consistent traffic, indicating that the project website served as a stable reference point for citizens and stakeholders seeking accessible information about the initiative.

At national level, capacity-building support through D1.3 demonstrated strong evidence of uptake, with 516 views and 382 downloads on Zenodo. This suggests that the guidance and templates were not only accessed but actively retrieved for potential reuse and adaptation, supporting the development of national communications and outreach strategies aligned with local context.

National tracking results indicate early but measurable progress in the development of 1+MG communication strategies between January 2025 and January 2026. While most Member States remain at an early or intermediate stage, fewer reported the absence of any strategy, and a small number reported nationally implemented approaches with dedicated funding. These findings confirm that strategy development is incremental and dependent on national capacity and resourcing.

Tracking of outreach video use at national level showed that uptake remains limited at this stage, with most Member States reporting that the videos are not yet in active use or are available only in English without broader promotion. Limited evidence of subtitle translation and campaign-based use reflects the early stage of national implementation and reinforces the importance of continued support, guidance and tracking to enable wider reuse over time.

A collaboration with EUPATI was established to engage its patient educator networks and facilitate national-level connections with 1+MG. Healthcare professional engagement progressed through structured consultation and survey development, with recommendations expected to be completed beyond the evaluation cut-off. Together, these strands support the continued need for structured stakeholder engagement approaches that connect European-level coordination with national-level delivery.

Overall, the results confirm that GDI communications and capacity-building work made a practical contribution to the 1+MG initiative by improving the availability of accessible materials, supporting national planning and providing a foundation for continued engagement activity through the Genome EDIC structure.

8. Next steps

The following next steps will support continued engagement and stronger national implementation:

1. **Continue dissemination and monitoring of citizen-facing resources**, including sustained promotion of the 1+MG video series and the "For citizens" website section.

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2. **Maintain national tracking through the 1+MG National Mirror Groups**, including follow-up tracking of video promotion and translation at Member State level.
3. **Strengthen patient educator engagement**, building on collaboration with EUPATI and supporting national-level linkages where relevant.
4. **Complete and disseminate healthcare professional recommendations**, including finalisation of survey outputs and development of practical guidance for awareness-raising and training.
5. **Update and disseminate D1.3 guidance**, incorporating implementation learning and stakeholder input, including updated guidance for video promotion and dissemination, and practical information to support ongoing collaboration

